

BUSINESS ECOSYSTEMS IN HEALTHCARE INDUSTRY: A FRAMEWORK OF ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Purpose – The current research aims to discover the main differences between the proposed linear model of business ecosystems structures in comparison to the classical model.

Methodology/approach - The current research resides on the proposed business ecosystem linear model of analysis. Thus, in this paper the research methodology is based on literature review in order to identify the main components of the proposed framework. Also, there was conducted an exploratory research and based on case study approach there was highlighted the main differences between the proposed and classical frameworks by gathering evidences from two companies.

Findings – The main result was to provide a new framework of business ecosystem analysis based on the evidence from the Health Care Industry. Also, to highlight the relevance of the linear business ecosystem model development in comparison to the classical one within the current state of the art.

Research limitations/implications – To propose an integrative framework applied in Health Care Industry as the main collaborative instrument whose main objective is to provide relevant insights on business ecosystems performance.

Practical implications – From this point of view, the proposed framework of analysis could provide an important mechanism applied in different industries in order to ensure business sustainable growth and performance measurement.

Originality/value – This paper demonstrates the relevance and applicability of the proposed customized business ecosystem framework by gathering the evidences from Health Care Industry.

Key words: Business ecosystems, Health Care Industry, Performance metrics

Introduction

Business ecosystem concept gained an increased attention especially as successful and collaborative structure which aims to ensure not only financial results for engaged stakeholders, but also to increase products attractivity for the final users. New technological changes (Caldwell, 2020), knowledge transfer processes, platforms creation, engaged collaborative experiences, actors' co-evolution (Peltoniemi, Vuori, 2004; Peltoniemi, 2005) represent a few principal motives for stakeholders' engagement into business ecosystems.

Proposed initially as a mechanism to explore and understand markets' dynamics (Moore, 1993), business ecosystem concept evolved as an integrative and complex framework. Interesting is the fact that business ecosystems development requires an integrative approach which transcends not only industry boarders but also eliminates the limitation among private and public sectors (Autio, 2022). From this point of view, business ecosystem's main objective seems to be closely linked to the delivering the co-created products (Jacobides, et. Al, 2018; Jacobides, Lianos, 2021). Thus, from the structural point of view, a modular approach is preferred.

Especially interesting for business ecosystems theory remains the structural organization of an entire community of actors (Adner, 2017, Aarikka-Stenrose, Ritala, 2017), as such collaborative structure requires not only to define orchestration processes, but also to understand what actors are engaging into this type of collaborative structure. From this point of view, a business ecosystem was defined as a

community comprised of suppliers, potential clients, distributors, standardization bodies (Moore, 1993; Makinen, Dedehayir, ...), governmental agencies (Galateanu (Avram), Avasilcai, 2013). However, the fact that in a business ecosystem could be engaged various actors the most valuable for its development was to define what roles those actors adopted. Thus, in the scientific literature emerged the first classification proposed by lansiti and Levien, namely: keystones, dominators, niche players and hub landlords (lansiti, Levien, 2004a). This classification was followed further by Den Hartigh who reshaped the roles and proposed new ones, such as: the shaper, the adapter and the opportunist (Den Hartigh, Tol, Visscher, 2006). Both theories suggested that each engaged actor from business ecosystem adopts a specific role in the main processes within the structure in accordance with the business ecosystem life cycle stage.

From this point of view, business ecosystems are relevant for actors' development especially through the lens of organizational transformation at each stage of its development, the created opportunities and evolving environments. Despite the fact that the academic community agreed upon the importance of business ecosystem's structure, life cycle stages of development, adopted roles and governance mechanisms, there still remains to fill the gap about ecosystems configurations which could bring those four aspects together in a symbiotic way.

At this point, the current research aimed to highlight the relevance of business ecosystem configuration and to explore its development in the Healthcare industry based on the proposed framework. The most valuable result was to understand the linkages among ecosystem structure, actors adopted roles and ecosystem performance.

Business Ecosystems in Healthcare Industry

The interest for Healthcare Industry and its development increased especially last years. The pandemic situation emergence triggered a series of industrial changes, an accelerated digital transformation process and the development of new emergent business ecosystems. During that period of time, the Healthcare industry became a pillar of national economies. Thus, exploration of healthcare business ecosystems represents an anchor point within current research.

According to the UN International Standard Classification, the Healthcare industry is concentrated on three main sectors such as: hospital activities, dental and medical activities and other healthcare services (United Nation Statistics Division, 2022). This statistic comprises a classification of actors by main function and provided products. Another classification was provided by Global Industry Classification Standard, according to which the healthcare industry is defined by: healthcare equipment and services, and pharmaceuticals, biotechnologies and natural sciences (MSCI, 2022). This type of classification is especially relevant in defining the healthcare business ecosystems as it gave the opportunity in identification of ecosystems engaged actors. Although up until now business ecosystems were presented from the actors' point of view, within the current research a customized approach was taken by bringing in front three main components, namely (Hernandez, et.al, 2009):

- Workforce – the existence of specialized employees such as medical one, auxiliar medical employees and non-medical personnel (administrative workforce, specialized in medical issues, non-governmental agencies – Red Cross, Doctors without Frontiers, etc.)
- Services – the interface offered within the doctor-client's relations. Usually, in the healthcare domain it is about the services offered by primary care physician.
- Systems – can be seen as an important infrastructure which could ensure the clients' access for medical services.

Research Methodology

In researching business ecosystem concept the anchor point is to understand the concept of collective effort and how it is quantified in different contexts. Up until now, the qualitative approach is preferred, especially from the explorative point of view, as its main interest is to understand and to provide an in-depth examination of business ecosystem concept (Yin, 2011). Thus, the adopted research methodology was based on the exploration of the business ecosystem formation phenomenon within Healthcare Industry. From this point of view, first undertaken step was to explore the structure of the analyzed industry in order to discover its constructive architecture based on Healthcare Industry metrics. Based on the identified structure of analyzed industry there were highlighted two main components:

pharmaceuticals, biotechnology and natural sciences, and healthcare services and equipment. However, within the proposed framework the second component was used as a unit of analysis. Next step in developing the analysis framework was to highlight and customize research criteria. Thus, based on literature review, there were proposed three main criteria of analysis such as: healthcare workforce, provided services and healthcare systems, applied on healthcare services and equipment component as it shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: The Healthcare Industry Business Ecosystem Framework

Consequently, the research strategy was based on the following stages:

- *exploration of healthcare industry especially within the private sector* – at this stage there were identified the main components within the healthcare industry used in the analysis framework development;
- *assessment of existing business ecosystem models* – there were proposed the units of analysis with respect to the initial theory of business ecosystems. Thus, based on literature review there were defined customized metrics based on actors' roles, ecosystems lifecycle and performance metrics;
- *provide illustration of framework analysis implementation* based on case study approach on two companies from the healthcare industry.

The Healthcare Industry Business Ecosystems: Fresenius versus Diaverum case study

In order to highlight how business ecosystems were formed within the healthcare industry, there was chosen two companies whose main objective is to provide healthcare services. From this point of view, based on secondary data there was provided an analysis on companies who provide the dialysis services such as Fresenius and Diaverum.

Fresenius Business Ecosystem Development and Analysis

Founded in 1912, Fresenius represents one of the global leaders in healthcare services providers with presence on over 100 countries (Fresenius, 2022a). Its successful development is based on the attention provided for the quality of the provided healthcare services, innovation and efficiency of the medical act (Fresenius, 2022a). According to historical milestones, the company expanded its own ecosystem not only through mergers and acquisitions, but also by creating its own divisions (Fresenius, 2022b), presented in figure 2. This type of linear growth ensured the coverage of all essential healthcare and social wellbeing services and extended the ecosystem as it follows: treatment services (Fresenius

Medical Care), creating own supply division (Fresenius Kabi), development and management of own healthcare facilities (Fresenius Vamed) and division responsible for the whole hospital network (Fresenius Helios) (Fresenius, 2022a).

Figure 2: Fresenius Business Ecosystem Structure

By analyzing Fresenius ecosystem development and life cycle it seems rather as a linear integration process. According to the secondary data, Fresenius ecosystem was developed synergically and in a constant manner. Once the company entered on the market (the birth stage), it shaped its own role further. Basically, the growth stage comprises the timeline when the company became a manufacturer and equipment supply of healthcare services – the division Fresenius Medical Care. In the growth stage the company ensured the diversification of its own offer and activities. By becoming the global leader as a supplier, Fresenius entered in the maturity stage of development. It ensures its domination by becoming not only globally recognized supplier but also the manufacturer of healthcare services. This was the moment when Fresenius established long term collaboration with InterWell Health in order to ensure best nephrologists services (Fresenius Medical Care, 2022) and other meaningful partnerships especially in the domain of kidney treatment processes and replacement – Unicyte, Humacyte, eGenesis (Kossmann, 2021) and it marked its transition from niche player to the keystone for other competitive ecosystems. The renewal of Fresenius ecosystem can be described by continuous effort to create new divisions. Also, during pandemic times, at this stage there were implemented digital platforms not only as the interface in relation medical staff-patient, but also digital warehouses of data (Stuard, Amato, 2021). Thus, by establishing divisions as Fresenius Helios and Vamed, the company gained new perspectives and opportunities to consolidate its position in Germany and Spain.

Consequently, by following life cycle stages, there can be seen that each actor from Fresenius ecosystem adopted its role as a part of strategic and sustainable growth goal, presented in table 1.

Table 1. The adopted roles of Fresenius business ecosystem actors

FRESENIUS	
Actors' roles	
Keystone players	Fresenius Medical Care
Niche players	Fresenius Medical Care Fresenius Kabi Fresenius Helios Fresenius Vamed
Dominators	Fresenius Medical Care
Hub landlords	Fresenius Medical Care

From the performance metrics point of view, Fresenius ecosystem seems to provide interesting insights. The company started its activity by providing dialysis services, developed until now in 4100 medical facilities in North America, Europe, Latin America, Asia Pacific and Africa. However, the continuous growth required also to expand their productivity line and diversification. From this point of view, by establishing Fresenius Kabi, the company ensured its own productivity by starting to produce specially designed medical equipment for dialysis and treatments for oncological and autoimmune diseases (Fresenius, 2022a). The resilience of this ecosystem can be explored through different metrics. From this point of view its survival rate, especially through pandemic times, is high as the company was able

to pass successfully the crisis of heparin (anticoagulant treatment for dialysis sessions) by initiating the production and introducing on the pharmaceutical market the Innohep (fractionated heparin that replaces the classic one in order to perform dialysis). Another key aspect which contributed to the development of resilient business ecosystem is closely linked by company development, namely: development of new divisions, creating its own business ecosystem actors and entering diverse niches, continuous diversification of the activities and products (medical services, healthcare equipment development, pharmaceuticals products, etc.)

Diaverum Business Ecosystem Development and Analysis

On the other side, the Diaverum’s business ecosystem model is rather based on classical model, initially proposed by Moore in 1993. Founded in Sweden in 1991, up until 2007 company concentrated its efforts on sustaining its own ecosystem at national level. However, at this moment it is globally present in over 24 countries, with over 12 thousand employees (Diaverum, 2022a). Diaverum’s core objective is to provide qualitative life-changing services (Diaverum, 2022a) and renal health services (Alharbi, A et al, 2020). Digitalization plays an essential role for the company, as it developed own healthcare platforms and application based on artificial intelligence (Diaverum, 2022b). Interesting is the fact that Diaverum’s business ecosystem structure depends on the development of collaboration with different partners and competitors such as: Nipro Japan and Fresenius Medical Care (dialysis equipment and accessories), Fresenius Kabi and Bbraun (medical equipment, medicamentation and chemical substances), as it is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Diaverum Business Ecosystem Structure

Established in 2007, as result of acquisition of Bidgepoint, represents the anchor point in the development of Diaverum Ecosystem, as it marked the birth stage. However, since 2007 up until 2022, the Diaverum ecosystem expanded so that it is represented by 155 medical facilities in 14 countries (Diaverum, 2022a). According to the official statement, nowadays it comprises 469 medical facilities providing dialysis services with over 41 thousand of patients (Diaverum, 2022a). A change of paradigm on the development of Diaverum ecosystem can be seen at the maturity stage. In order to stay competitive within the healthcare industry, the company addressed to international suppliers such as Baxter, Nipro and Bbraun on from the dialysis equipment and accesories point of view (Diaverum, 2022d). Thus, in order to sustain its business ecosystem, Diaverum in the renewal stage started to incorporate ambulatory monitoring offices, as example the ambulatory network from South Arabia recognized and accredited by Joint Commission International (Diaverum, 2022a). This approach was preferred in order to attract patients to the Diaverum clinics and to get them to know the Diaverum’s staff, medical facilities and services offered by each clinic. Also, as a part of renewal ecosystem strategy the company engaged into long-term partnership with Spanish Confederation of Business Organization

(Diaverum, 2022e) In comparison with the previous case, the Diaverum ecosystem is highly anchored to the main goal, that is to provide dialysis services. From this point of view, the actors who are engaging into this ecosystem were mostly external partners, whose roles are presented in the table 2.

Table 2. The adopted roles of Diaverum business ecosystem actors

DIAPERUM	
Actors' roles	
Keystone players	Diaverum
Niche players	Nipro Japan Fresenius Medical Care Fresenius Kabi Bbraun
Dominators	Fresenius Medical Care
Hub landlords	Diaverum

Productivity metrics are strictly confirmed by the numbers stated officially, that means that Diaverum's ecosystem serves up to 41 thousand of patients through 469 medical facilities worldwide (Diaverum, 2022a). However, there is no change from the product or service point of view as Diaverum does not provide diversification of the services (other than dialysis treatment). Consequently, in order to sustain its own productivity Diaverum looked for another strategy which meant to establish nephrology monitoring points. From the resilience point of view, Diaverum followed up its long-term strategy. Basically, one of the strategic decisions during ecosystem's development was to address to various supply companies of medical and infusible treatments equipment and dialysis equipment (Diaverum, 2022d).

Fresenius versus Diaverum Business Ecosystems

In the current research there were presented two different business ecosystems within the healthcare industry. The main criteria of comparison between those two cases were: ecosystem structure, actors' roles within the ecosystem, the life cycle and performance metrics. In order to illustrate the main differences, there was realized an extensive analysis presented in the table 3.

Table 3. Comparative analysis based on the main criteria: business ecosystem life cycle and performance metrics

	FRESENIUS	DIAPERUM
Business Ecosystem Life Cycle Stages		
Birth stage	Once the company was founded	
Growth stage	Activity diversity by establishing 4 new divisions	Geographical expansion, new markets penetration
Maturity stage	Global leader in medical equipment and services	Recognition in top 3 on dialysis services
Renewal Stage	Diversification of the products, became major European operator of the network of private medical facilities	Extends its activity by establishing new monitoring points
Business Ecosystems Metrics		
Productivity		
• Product performance	Dialysis services at large scale	Dialysis services at middle scale
• Productivity change	Medical equipment manufacturing, pharmaceuticals products and hospitals' network	Dialysis services
• Innovation	Medication for oncological and dialysis treatments	Network of new monitoring medical point

Resilience			
• Survival Rate		High level of adaptation to the crisis moments within the healthcare industry	
• Ecosystem structure adaptability		Restructuring of the entire group by adding new divisions	Adaptability of the organizational structure based on new supply actor's emergence
• Predictability		Unpredictable growth rate and continuous innovation	Predictable growth rate based on the main goal
• Obsolence		Low level	High Level
• Learning from experience		Self-sustaining business ecosystem	Business ecosystem based on competitors' actions

Discussions and conclusion

Nowadays, the healthcare industry pasted and is passing continuous changing especially in the private sector. The current research aimed to illustrate how the concept of business ecosystem can be applied within this industry by putting an accent especially in the service part, for our case study we have chosen to concentrate on dialysis services. At global level, the dialysis services are ensured by various actors, however in top three are Fresenius, Braun and Diaverum. By analyzing the healthcare industry there was projected the initial framework, which stated clearly which are the main component of the industry to be further explored. However, the main concern of the analysis was concentrated on the healthcare services and equipment component.

According to the performed analysis there can be seen that Fresenius ecosystem is more evolved than Diaverum. Fresenius was rather concentrated on niche creation by restructuring and creating new and own satellites companies. From the point of view of sustainable growth, new divisions creation was the best choice, especially during pandemic times as the company created required dialysis and other medical equipment for own and not only use. Also, by expanding its own activity through new divisions creation, Fresenius could adopt within its own business ecosystem different roles, such as: keystone (by being a supply actor for other ecosystems), dominator (by owning its own manufacturing facilities) and niche player. This type of ecosystem growth seems to be more adapted to the current needs in the healthcare industry as it is suggestion a linear type of development. However, the main arising threat is about increasing the domination on other actors from the healthcare industry and obstruction of new entrants in business ecosystems. Basically, it is forming new type of self-sustainable ecosystem. The fact that is in opposite side than initial theory of what a business ecosystem means.

On the other side, there was presented the case of Diaverum, an ecosystem entirely based on providing the dialysis services. Diaverum's ecosystem was outlined according to the classical model, initially proposed by James Moore. According to the findings, this type of ecosystem within the healthcare industry is less performing especially within the current research. However, it seems interesting the fact that in order to sustain its own ecosystem, Diaverum had to increase the number of ambulatory offices. The main concern was to increase the collaboration with the final user from informative point of view. However, as for actor role, Diaverum represents a keystone especially in dialysis services and is an active actor in the relation with the academia on research part.

In terms of performance metrics, the comparative analysis shows a higher productivity for the linear model of business ecosystem growth, a higher resilience and innovation rate for the same type of framework. However, the classical model of business ecosystem presents more predictable mechanisms of business growth, as the unit of analysis was chosen from the private sector. The main distinction between those two ecosystems was rather about the used growth strategy.

As conclusion, there can be stated that linear business ecosystem is more performant than classical one, but with the respect to the adopted strategy: to be a keystone on own ecosystem or dominator.

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